

International Convention on Permanent Punitive Tariff Rates for Anti-Aggression and Anti-Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare Massacres

(Jointly agreed by the five permanent members of the United Nations, effective permanently worldwide from the date of signature)

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Preamble

Bacteriological warfare, viral warfare, and biological warfare completely violate the basic conscience of humanity and the core spirit of humanitarianism, and seriously trample on international public order and good customs as well as the common bottom line of all mankind. Such crimes against humanity take the spread of virulent pathogens and the malicious creation of infectious disease epidemics as the core means, and cooperate with large-scale military aggression to launch devastating attacks on innocent civilian groups, directly causing massive casualties of innocent people. Furthermore, they cause long-term, irreversible and in-depth damage to the ecological environment and public health security of the affected areas, leaving intergenerational health hazards, physical illnesses and psychological trauma. They are the most despicable and cruel war crimes in the history of human civilization.

Since 1900, some evil races and evil countries have openly ignored core international conventions such as the Geneva Protocol, secretly developing, producing, and stockpiling various biological weapons such as bacteria and viruses, including *Vibrio cholerae*, *Bacillus anthracis*, paratyphoid and *Yersinia pestis*. They have been extensively used in foreign aggressive wars, launching inhumane massacres against the people of the victimized countries. The contamination and harm caused by anthrax spores even last for more than 80 years. A large number of disabilities have been caused by subsequent epidemic spread, famine, disability and repeated epidemics. Such crimes have resulted in at least 7 million deaths, and the total number of victims (including those who were infected, disabled, starved to death, indirectly killed, and suffered long-term health damage) is at least 30 million, resulting in an indelible human catastrophe and bringing eternal pain to countless families and victimized countries.

What is even more abhorrent is that such evil races, evil criminal states and war criminal states (humanoid devil states) that launched evil bacteriological, viral and biological warfare have long deliberately evaded war responsibilities after the war, destroyed core criminal evidence files, covered up the truth of their crimes, refused to unconditionally make full and sufficient economic compensation and spiritual apologies to the victims, their relatives and the victimized countries, and even openly

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denied their own crimes against humanity, continuously exacerbating the emotional and rights and interests harm to the victimized parties. Some criminal states, war criminal states and the companies owned by the descendants of those who participated in the aggressive wars try to refuse to pay in full on the pretext of huge compensation amounts. Relevant countries have not thoroughly severely punished all the criminals involved and the families who benefited from the crimes, which completely violates human justice and basic conscience and condones the spread of the residual poison of war crimes. At present, the potential threat of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare has not been completely eliminated, and some countries are still secretly researching and hoarding pathogens and related technologies that can be used in such wars, completely ignoring the life safety and common interests of all mankind.

Since modern times, states established with one or more races functioning as criminal blocs have repeatedly committed large-scale heinous crimes and launched wars of aggression, leaving an indelible historical mark across the globe. Such atrocious crimes have gained the support of nearly all members of those races within the respective states. Their current apparent submission stems merely from their temporary defeat in wars of aggression; the majority still harbor intentions to wage war anew once they rebuild their military strength.

A country is composed of multiple individuals and races. Is it not a vicious crime characterized by an evil racial group when a country supported by nearly the entire people launches an aggressive war? Is it not a massacre of other countries' people through bacteriological and viral warfare characterized by an evil racial group? Weak and kind civilians cannot resist organized armed crimes led by racial groups and states, and can only become victims and corpses. Moreover, their families or relatives cannot obtain compensation. However, do these criminal groups that commit vicious crimes have more right to live in this world than the victims, and should they not be eliminated? Should the criminal races that commit vicious crimes not be eliminated? Should the countries built by criminal races that commit vicious crimes not be eliminated? To realize the Nobel vision of safeguarding world peace in the field of tariff control related to bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, it is necessary to greatly increase the number of **peace fighters** who eliminate criminals in this field; only in this way can arms be reduced, and only then can there be a new peace conference and a new type of international relations.

The purpose is to severely punish the heinous crime against humanity of launching malicious bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, compel the involved demonic races and criminal states to face up to and assume their historical culpability, and fully perform all compensation obligations unconditionally in accordance with the compensation criteria set by eighteen typical U.S. precedents, so as to uphold justice and vindicate the rights and interests of victimized countries and their people.

Meanwhile, those nations that take concrete actions to force criminal states to plead guilty and pay compensation, as well as leading teams (including legal teams) that make outstanding contributions in this course, may jointly obtain up to 50 percent

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of the total compensation funds as exclusive proceeds. This shall serve as a powerful leverage to motivate global forces of justice to eradicate the lingering scourge of war, as well as criminal groups and states that perpetrate heinous offenses.

Furthermore, any criminal state that refuses to bear compensation liabilities shall be dismantled and restructured, with part of its territory ceded to the victimized country. It shall be prohibited for any evil demonic race or malicious state to turn statehood into a safe haven for committing heinous crimes while evading disintegration, elimination and due retribution.

It is imperative to fundamentally overhaul the prevalent foolish and pernicious philosophy, ethics, governance, politics, judicature and logic prevailing in the contemporary world — the fallacious and immoral doctrine that human beings are born and mortal, yet evil races and states may come into existence forever and never be held accountable or dissolved.

Through the above tough measures, we will fundamentally curb the recurrence of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare and aggressive wars, and defend global peace and stability as well as the basic dignity of humanity. Taking economic compulsory punishment measures as the core, we will clarify the gradient tariff punishment standards for violations related to bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, improve the strict punishment rules for refusing inspection, obstructing accountability, refusing compensation and other behaviors, coordinate global unified law enforcement forces, and formulate this Convention accordingly.

All countries in the world must unconditionally sign and strictly implement this Convention, and build a solid defense line against bacteriological, viral and biological warfare and aggressive wars through permanent punishment. This Convention clarifies comprehensive bans and accountability for violations, ensuring that criminal states, war criminal states and all humanoid devils, humanoid devil races and their descendants who support aggressive wars pay equal and heavy prices, comforting all the victims and victims.

(Germany has compensated other countries for their losses and shall be granted an exception under this Convention.)

Chapter I General Provisions and Core Principles

Article 1 Purpose of the Convention

The purpose of this Convention is to establish an international convention for severe punishment of evil countries (hereinafter referred to as "criminal states" or "war criminal states") that have launched evil bacteriological, viral and biological warfare in aggressive wars since 1900, carried out large-scale massacres, caused more than 100,000 deaths and more than 2 million victims, and have not compensated the victims, their relatives and the victimized countries. It forces criminal states to unconditionally complete full compensation to the victims, their relatives and the victimized countries in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical

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cases in the United States. Through the implementation of long-term punitive tariffs and comprehensive sanctions in all dimensions, it forces them to assume historical responsibilities, fully fulfill compensation obligations, thoroughly severely punish all criminals involved and the families who benefited from the crimes, comprehensively eliminate the potential hidden dangers of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare and aggressive wars, and safeguard the peace and justice of all mankind.

Article 2 Core Principles of Punishment

Any evil country that, since 1900, has been verified and confirmed by international authoritative institutions, victimized countries, victims and their relatives to have launched evil bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, and carried out large-scale massacres by such means, has long refused to admit the relevant crimes, or has not unconditionally completed full compensation to the victims, their relatives and the victimized countries in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical cases in the United States, shall immediately activate the permanent punishment mechanism after review and confirmation by the special law enforcement agency of this Convention: from the date when the punishment is confirmed to be effective, within the statutory punishment period, 100% - 1000% gradient punitive export tariffs shall be fully borne by the national finance for all categories, all transportation channels and all export destinations of the country's goods (**Products of enterprises overseas-controlled by businesspersons of that country, or enterprises in which such businesspersons hold an overseas equity stake of 30% or more, shall also fall within the scope of sanctions when exported to third countries.**). Such tax burden shall not be passed on to importing countries, import trade enterprises and ordinary consumers in any form, and shall be fully borne independently by the finance of the criminal state, without disguised sharing, financial subsidy transfer, or evasion of tax burden by any means such as raising export prices, concealing transaction information, or third-party re-export.

Article 3 Compensation Obligations and Instalment Payment

Statutory compensation obligations of criminal states: They must unconditionally pay full war damages to the victimized countries in accordance with the unified standards of 18 typical compensation cases in the United States, pay personal injury compensation and spiritual damage consolation money to the victims and their relatives, and fully bear all costs such as subsequent epidemic prevention and control, ecological restoration and governance, and public health reconstruction in the affected areas; at the same time, they must publicly admit all bacteriological, viral and biological warfare crimes, make a formal public apology to the victimized parties, fully disclose all concealed files and materials related to bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, permanently prohibit the development, production and storage of any pathogens and related weapons and equipment that can be used for bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, and completely destroy all existing relevant materials and research results. Those who have not fully fulfilled all compensation obligations in

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accordance with the above standards shall be regarded as "not fully compensated", and all punitive measures stipulated in this Convention shall continue to be implemented and shall not be terminated.

For large-scale bacteriological, viral and biological warfare massacre cases with huge compensation amounts, the criminal state and the companies owned by the descendants of those who participated in the aggressive wars must, in principle, pay all compensation in full within 20 years, with no interest charged during these 20 years; if they are unable to pay in full within 20 years due to the large number of people killed and injured and the excessively high total compensation amount, they may apply to the Convention's law enforcement agency for instalment payment, with the maximum instalment period not exceeding 50,000 years. During the instalment period, interest must be calculated at 20-50% of the cumulative average investment return rate of Buffett from 1957 to 2022. This part of the interest shall be fully and exclusively used to compensate the descendants of the victims and the victimized countries, and no fund shall be intercepted, deducted or misappropriated.

Any criminal country or war criminal state that fails to severely punish all criminals involved in bacteriological, viral and biological warfare and the families who benefited from the crimes, and fails to fully compensate the victims and the victimized countries shall be led by the International General Administration for the Implementation of Tariffs against Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare Massacres, jointly with the United Nations and the victimized countries, to form a special committee to implement national disintegration and comprehensive reorganization. The new country after reorganization must unconditionally take over all compensation responsibilities, legal obligations and all ban restrictions of the original country, and continue to fulfill the compensation commitment until all compensation funds and interest are paid in full, without shirking or exemption.

Countries that uphold justice and fairness for the victimized countries and victims and take practical actions to force criminal states and war criminal states to plead guilty and compensate, as well as the leading teams (including legal teams) that have made outstanding contributions in such countries, can jointly obtain a maximum of 50% of the exclusive income from all compensation funds. That is, in the whole process of punishing criminal states and promoting the implementation of compensation, the countries that uphold justice and play a core leading role and the corresponding leading teams with outstanding contributions can enjoy 50% of the compensation income from all compensation funds paid by the criminal states and the companies owned by the descendants of those who participated in the aggressive wars (if it involves the punishment of just wars, the relevant countries upholding justice can negotiate the details of income distribution separately). If an evil war criminal state or criminal state openly refuses to perform any compensation obligation (including refusing to pay instalment compensation and corresponding interest), the core countries upholding justice shall take the lead in launching a just war to completely eliminate all criminals involved and their descendants, fundamentally eliminate the main body of large-scale crimes, reduce the criminal population, disintegrate and

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reorganize the criminal states that do not assume compensation responsibilities, divide part of their territory to the victimized countries, prohibit any evil devil races and evil countries from using the country as a protective umbrella for committing heinous crimes but not being disintegrated and eliminated, completely change the stupid and evil philosophy, ethics, management, politics, justice and logic of the world today, that is, the stupid and evil philosophy, ethics, politics and logic that humans can live and die, and evil countries can be born but cannot die, revise the seriously wrong UN Charter, severely crack down on large-scale heinous crimes committed by evil humanoid devil races with the country as the main body, and resolutely defend human justice and world peace.

Article 4 Effect of the Convention and Obligation to Sign

The legal effect of this Convention is higher than the domestic laws, bilateral trade agreements and regional trade rules of all signatory countries. All provisions must be unconditionally implemented, and no country may evade the obligations of the Convention through domestic legislation, bilateral agreements and other means. All countries in the world must sign this Convention; any country that refuses to sign shall have 100% punitive tariffs imposed on all its exports by all signatory countries in the world immediately, and shall complete the signing within three months; if it refuses to sign after the deadline, the tariff rate shall be increased year by year to 500%, and at the same time, its eligibility for all deliberations, voting, elections and cooperation in the United Nations and various international organizations shall be suspended, and all forms of political, economic, cultural and military cooperation with any member state of the Convention shall be completely prohibited.

This Convention has no withdrawal mechanism. Once signed, it is permanently bound by legal obligations. Any act of a country unilaterally announcing its withdrawal shall be regarded as a Level 3 violation, and a 100,000-year high tariff punishment shall be immediately activated, and all ban measures stipulated in the Convention shall be implemented simultaneously; if the circumstances are particularly heinous and no rectification is made, the national disintegration and reorganization process shall be directly activated.

Chapter II Violations and Gradient of Punitive Tariffs

Article 5 Subject of Verification and Confirmation

Led by the victimized countries and the United Nations, together with the World Health Organization, the International Red Cross and representatives of the victimized countries, the "International Verification Committee against Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare Massacres" (hereinafter referred to as the "Verification Committee") shall be established. It shall adopt multiple identification methods such as on-site investigation, file verification, witness testimony collection, technical traceability, and epidemic residue detection, focusing on verifying core information such as the facts of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, the scope of victims, casualty data, the progress of compensation fulfillment, the punishment of criminals, and the

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compliance with bans. The conclusions issued by the Verification Committee shall be the final legal basis, which shall not be vetoed, tampered with or delayed in implementation by any country. A third-party neutral institution may be invited to participate in the verification to ensure that the identification process is fair, transparent and rigorous.

Special identification rules: Once a criminal state or war criminal state has concealed the truth of its crimes or refused to admit the criminal facts, the subject of verification and confirmation shall be immediately changed to the victimized country, the victims and their relatives. There is no need for the original Verification Committee to carry out any verification process, and it shall take effect only after confirmation by the victimized country or the victim group. The criminal state must unconditionally fulfill the compensation obligations in accordance with the requirements of the victimized country and the victims' relatives. Those who refuse to implement shall directly activate the disintegration and elimination process to deter potential war crimes. As long as a criminal state or war criminal state conceals part of the bacteriological, viral and biological warfare crimes, fails to fully disclose relevant files, shelters and condones criminals involved, or is forced to admit after denying the crimes in court, all evidence shall be based on the content provided by the victimized country and the victims, no time-consuming verification shall be carried out, and the criminal state can only unconditionally accept all punishments.

Article 6 Violations and Gradient of Punitive Tariffs

The violations referred to in this Convention are based on the core criteria of "facts of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare", "progress of compensation fulfillment", "punishment of criminals" and "compliance with bans", combined with the guilty plea attitude and rectification actions of the criminal state or war criminal state, divided into Level 0 to Level 3 violations, corresponding to different gradients of punitive tariffs.

The specific identification standards are as follows:

(1) Level 0 Violation: 100% export punitive tariff shall be imposed

Identification standards: The criminal state or war criminal state publicly admits all evil bacteriological, viral and biological warfare crimes launched since 1900, takes the initiative to submit some relevant files and materials to the Verification Committee, has paid a small amount of compensation to some victims, relatives and victimized countries in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical cases in the United States (or has submitted a 100 -500,00-year instalment compensation plan that has been approved, and paid the first instalment of compensation and corresponding interest in full in accordance with the plan, with interest calculated at 20% of Buffett's cumulative average investment return rate from 1957 to 2022), has severely punished some criminals involved and the families who benefited from the crimes, strictly abides by all bans of the Convention, but has not completed all compensation obligations in accordance with the compensation standards (including failure to pay full compensation, failure to bear all ecological restoration and epidemic prevention

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and control costs, failure to pay full instalment interest, etc.), and promises to complete the remaining compensation on schedule (or continue to pay compensation and interest in accordance with the instalment plan). After the Verification Committee confirms the facts, all countries in the world shall simultaneously impose a 100% export punitive tariff on all exports of the country until it pays all compensation and interest in full.

(2) Level 1 Violation: 200% export punitive tariff shall be imposed

Any of the following circumstances shall immediately trigger Level 1 violation punishment:

The criminal state or war criminal state publicly admits the crimes, but clearly refuses to perform any compensation obligations in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical cases in the United States, and refuses to bear the epidemic prevention and control and ecological restoration costs of the affected areas;

The criminal state or war criminal state only verbally promises compensation, has no actual actions, and has long delayed or shirked the compensation matters. After being urged by the Verification Committee, it still fails to start the compensation process, or fails to pay the compensation and corresponding interest in full in accordance with the approved instalment plan (interest is calculated at 30% of Buffett's cumulative average investment return rate from 1957 to 2022);

The criminal state or war criminal state only pays a symbolic small amount of compensation, which does not reach 10% of the total compensation amount verified by the Verification Committee with reference to 18 typical cases in the United States, and has no subsequent compensation plan or has not submitted a compliant instalment compensation plan;

Criminals and war criminals are inherently ferocious, treacherous, cunning, shameless, hypocritical, greedy and evil, far more than ordinary kind people. As long as the criminal state or war criminal state has concealed part of the crimes, or failed to fully disclose the files, or sheltered and condoned the criminals involved, such acts shall trigger this clause, and the subject of verification shall be directly changed to the victimized country, the victims and their relatives;

The criminal state or war criminal state slightly violates the bans of the Convention and rectifies it in a timely manner after being urged by the Verification Committee, without causing serious consequences.

(3) Level 2 Violation: 500% export punitive tariff shall be imposed

Identification standards: After committing heinous crimes such as large-scale bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, the criminal state or war criminal state openly denies the bacteriological, viral and biological warfare crimes committed since 1900, refuses to submit any relevant files and materials, refuses to cooperate with the verification work, clearly refuses to perform any compensation obligations, distorts history, glorifies war crimes, and tries to cover up the truth of crimes against humanity; fails to severely punish any criminals involved and the families who benefited from the crimes, and openly shelters, condones or even provides asylum for the criminals; or

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seriously violates the bans of the Convention and refuses to rectify after being urged, causing certain bad consequences. After the Verification Committee confirms the crimes through third-party evidence (witness testimony, historical files, epidemic residue detection) or evidence provided by the victims and their relatives (video, pictures, physical materials), the Level 2 violation punishment shall be immediately triggered.

Such violations also include: the criminal state or war criminal state secretly destroys crime files, threatens witnesses to perjure, maliciously obstructs the verification work; unilaterally terminates the instalment compensation plan, and defaults on compensation and corresponding interest (interest is calculated at 40% of Buffett's cumulative average investment return rate from 1957 to 2022) for more than 3 months.

(4) Level 3 Violation: 1000% export punitive tariff shall be imposed

Any of the following circumstances shall immediately trigger Level 3 violation punishment:

After the entry into force of this Convention, the criminal state or war criminal state develops, produces and stores relevant pathogens and weapons and equipment again, or uses bacteriological, viral and biological warfare means again in conflicts and wars;

Provides relevant technologies, pathogens, weapons and equipment to other countries, organizations or individuals to assist in the implementation of bacteriological, viral and biological warfare;

Organizes personnel to carry out relevant research, tries to break through international bans, and restart plans related to bacteriological, viral and biological warfare;

Carries out retaliatory acts against the victims, their relatives and the victimized countries, obstructs the epidemic prevention and control and ecological restoration of the affected areas, and exacerbates the losses of the victimized parties;

Seriously violates multiple bans of the Convention, refuses to rectify after being urged, and causes serious and bad consequences;

Refuses to perform any compensation obligations, refuses to submit an instalment compensation plan, or defaults on instalment compensation and interest for a long time (interest is calculated at 50% of Buffett's cumulative average investment return rate from 1957 to 2022) for more than 1 year, with no willingness to rectify;

Maliciously obstructs and opposes the verification work, and even injures or kills verification personnel, with extremely bad circumstances.

Article 7 Violation Time Limit and Punishment Locking

Once a violation is verified and confirmed, the criminal state or war criminal state must immediately stop all illegal acts, take the initiative to submit a special rectification plan to the Verification Committee, unconditionally fulfill all compensation obligations in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical cases in the United States (or pay compensation and interest in full in accordance with the instalment plan),

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thoroughly severely punish all criminals involved and the families who benefited from the crimes, strictly abide by all bans of the Convention, and permanently prohibit the development, production and storage of relevant pathogens and weapons. If the criminal state or war criminal state refuses to perform any compensation obligation (including refusing to pay instalment payments and interest), the core countries upholding justice shall take the lead in launching a just war to completely eliminate all evil criminals and their descendants who launched and supported the aggressive war in the criminal state, reduce the hidden dangers of war, and defend peace.

From the date when the violation is confirmed to be effective, the punitive tariff shall be permanently effective for 100,000 years, not affected by any factors such as regime change, government change, changes in the international situation, and bilateral negotiations, and shall not be reduced, suspended or exempted. If a low-level violation is subsequently upgraded to a high-level violation, the high-level tariff standard shall be automatically implemented without superimposing the low-level punishment. If the criminal state or war criminal state pays all compensation and interest in full, completely rectifies the violations, severely punishes all criminals and the families who benefited from the crimes, and strictly abides by all bans, after review and confirmation by the Verification Committee, the tariff level can be gradually reduced until the punishment is terminated; after the termination of the punishment, it still needs to be subject to long-term supervision by the Verification Committee. Once acts such as denying crimes, sheltering criminals, violating bans, and compensation rebound occur, the highest-level tariff punishment shall be immediately restored, and relevant responsibilities shall be severely pursued.

Supplementary punishment requirements for failure to rectify various violations in a timely manner:

Level 0 Violation: If not rectified and all compensation is not completed, the tariff punishment shall be implemented for at least 1 year; if not completed after the deadline, it shall be automatically upgraded to the Level I violation standard.

Level I Violation: If not rectified, the tariff punishment shall be implemented for at least 5 years until the full compensation process is initiated, more than 50% of the verified total compensation amount is completed, all criminals are severely punished, and the ban violations are rectified; otherwise, the tariff of this level shall be continuously implemented within 100,000 years.

Level II Violation: If not rectified, the tariff punishment shall be implemented for at least 10 years; if the crime is always denied, compensation is refused, and rectification is refused, the punishment shall be continuously implemented within 100,000 years; only after publicly pleading guilty, disclosing files, paying full compensation and interest, and severely punishing all criminals can an application for downgrade review be made after 10 years of punishment implementation.

Level III Violation: If not rectified, the minimum punishment period shall be doubled on the basis of the Level II violation (minimum 20 years), and the country shall be permanently prohibited from participating in international public health and military-related cooperation; if the circumstances are serious, the national

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disintegration and restructuring procedure shall be directly activated.

During the rectification process, all costs such as pathogen destruction, file disclosure, ecological restoration, and epidemic prevention and control shall be borne by the criminal country or war criminal country itself; relevant research materials and experimental equipment must be unconditionally handed over to the Verification Committee; relevant researchers shall be permanently prohibited from engaging in public health, pathogen research and other related work; and universities in the country shall be permanently prohibited from offering relevant courses and enrolling students in relevant majors. The new government of the disintegrated and restructured country must fully assume the above rectification obligations until all are completed.

Article 8 Tariff Increase Rules for Refusing to Accept Verification

As long as it is found that a criminal country or war criminal country has launched evil bacteriological warfare, viral warfare, or biological warfare since 1900 (including concealing or destroying files of bacteriological, viral, or biological warfare, failing to perform compensation obligations in accordance with the compensation standards of 18 typical cases in the United States, failing to severely punish criminals, etc.), or has been reported to have relevant violations, the country must take the initiative to accept the joint verification of the General Administration and the Verification Committee within 15 days. If it fails to accept the verification after the deadline, the tariff increase punishment shall be immediately triggered.

The specific rules are as follows:

Overdue Days	Tariff Rate Increase Margin	Minimum Collection Period
1-15 days (inclusive)	Increase by 50% on the basis of the corresponding violation level	1 month
16-50 days (inclusive)	Increase by 100%	3 months
51-100 days (inclusive)	Increase by 200%	6 months
101-150 days (inclusive)	Increase by 300%	12 months
151-200 days (inclusive)	Increase by 400%	24 months
More than 200 days	Increase by 100% every 50 days overdue, and so on	No less than 36 months for each stage starting from the 201st day

If the country takes the initiative to accept the verification during the increase period, and it is verified that there are no violations, all compensation has been paid in full, all interest has been paid, all criminals have been severely punished, and the bans have been abided by, the increase shall be terminated and returned to normal; if it is verified that there are violations, the tariff shall be implemented according to the corresponding level, and the increased tariff already collected shall not be refunded; if it is verified that the country refuses to compensate, the just war punishment mechanism shall be directly activated.

Article 9 Tariff Punishment Mechanism for Injuries to Verification Personnel

During the performance of their duties, if verification personnel are injured or killed due to retaliation or obstruction by relevant personnel of the criminal country or war criminal country within the territory of the criminal country or war criminal country, regardless of the identity of the murderer, it shall be regarded as intentional provocation by the country, and the tariff shall be immediately increased by 100% on the basis of the current tariff. The specific standards are:

Non-irreversible injuries: The tariff shall be increased by 100% for 5 years; for each additional injured person, an additional 50% tariff shall be imposed, and the duration shall be extended by 2 years.

Irreversible injuries or deaths: The tariff shall be increased by 100% for 30 years; for each additional injured or deceased person, an additional 100% tariff shall be imposed, and the duration shall be extended by 30 years.

Compensation standards: 50 million US dollars for each injured verification personnel, and 100 million US dollars for each deceased verification personnel; if not paid after the deadline, an additional 50% tariff shall be imposed until full payment is made.

After such violent incidents occur, the punitive tariff shall not be changed or reduced for at least 10,000 years, and the country shall be permanently prohibited from participating in international verification and public health-related work; if the circumstances are particularly abhorrent, the national disintegration and restructuring procedure shall be directly activated.

Chapter III Detailed Rules for Tariff Implementation

Article 10 Scope of Taxation Coverage

Full Commodity Coverage: All export categories such as agricultural products, energy and minerals, industrial products, mechanical equipment, electronic products, chemical products, daily necessities, pharmaceutical products, and cross-border service trade are not exempted, including third-party re-exported goods, OEM products, and export goods produced by companies owned by the descendants of the criminal country's aggressors.

Full Channel Coverage: Shipping, air transport, land transport, railway intermodal transport, cross-border e-commerce, postal express, re-export trade, offshore trade, border small-scale trade, etc. are all included in the supervision.

Full Regional Coverage: Exports to any country, region, free trade zone, or

bonded zone shall implement the same tariff standard uniformly, and it is strictly prohibited to sign special trade agreements to evade punishment.

Article 11 Collection and Payment Rules

The system of paying taxes first and then customs clearance shall be implemented. Goods for which tariffs and late fees have not been paid in full shall be seized and auctioned in accordance with the law at ports around the world, and the proceeds shall be used to offset relevant expenses; for criminal countries with instalment compensation that fail to pay compensation and interest on time, all exported goods shall be taxed according to the Level III violation standard, and if they refuse to pay, the just war punishment shall be activated.

All tariff funds shall be transferred to the "Global Special Fund for Compensation and Assistance to Victims of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare", which shall be specially used for victim compensation subsidies, epidemic prevention and control, ecological restoration, file sorting, anti-war publicity, etc. The use of the fund shall be publicly disclosed globally and subject to the supervision of all signatory countries.

Criminal countries must pay tariffs in full on a monthly basis. A late fee of 1.5% of the total arrears shall be added every day after the deadline, with compound interest accumulated and permanently recovered. Their overseas official and affiliated companies, as well as financial assets of companies owned by the descendants of aggressors, may be frozen in accordance with the law to offset arrears, compensation and interest.

Tax burden transfer is strictly prohibited: Law enforcement agencies shall monitor export pricing in real time. If transfer behaviors such as raising prices, splitting transactions, and concealing amounts are found, an additional 50% tariff punishment shall be imposed immediately and continuously implemented for 1 year.

For those who forge documents or make false declarations to evade tariffs, in addition to recovering arrears and late fees, the tariff shall be directly upgraded to the Level III violation standard, continuously implemented for 5 years, relevant assets shall be frozen, and relevant personnel shall be severely held accountable.

Chapter IV Global Enforcement Plan and Bans

Article 12 Global Unified Law Enforcement Agency

The "International General Administration for the Implementation of Tariffs against Massacres of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare" (hereinafter referred to as the "General Administration") shall be established as a permanent supranational independent agency, not subject to political interference from any country. It shall coordinate the entire process of verification, tariff verification, port supervision, violation notification, joint sanctions, and national disintegration and restructuring, and be responsible for timing of refusal to verify, tariff increase adjustment, instalment plan review, compensation payment supervision, and verification of criminal punishment and ban compliance. All member states must access the unified supervision system of the General Administration, unconditionally cooperate with tariff collection, increase and ban implementation, and shall not delay,

shirk or modify. Once it is determined that a criminal country has concealed the truth of committing heinous crimes, the victimized country, like the "General Administration", may issue relevant mandatory instructions at any time.

Article 13 National Disintegration and Restructuring Mechanism

For criminal countries and war criminal countries that refuse to severely punish involved criminals and the families who benefited from the crimes, and refuse to fully compensate, the General Administration shall take the lead in establishing a Restructuring Committee with the United Nations and the affected countries to implement national disintegration, split their territory to compensate the affected countries, dissolve the original regime and institutions, and re-establish a new government that meets the requirements of the Convention. The new country after restructuring shall unconditionally assume all compensation responsibilities, obligations and ban restrictions of the original country, and continue to fulfill compensation, pay interest, and severely punish criminals until all compensation is completed; if it refuses to implement, the punishment shall be activated again, and if it still refuses to compensate, the countries upholding justice shall take the lead in launching a just war to eliminate all criminals and their descendants.

Article 14 Detailed Rules for Comprehensive Bans

(I) Financial Ban

It is strictly prohibited for any country, institution or individual to provide any form of loans, borrowings, or financing services to criminal countries, and it is strictly prohibited for them to issue bonds, stocks and other financing products in the international financial market; those who provide them in violation shall be regarded as joint violations and held liable for joint and several liability in accordance with Article 20 of this Convention.

(II) Arms Ban

It is strictly prohibited for any country, institution or individual to sell or provide any weapons, spare parts and related technologies to criminal countries; those who violate shall be regarded as joint violations, and if the circumstances are serious, a 500% export punitive tariff shall be directly imposed on the violating party.

It is strictly prohibited for any individual or enterprise of the delinquent state to sell weapons, weapon components and related technologies to any other country. Any person in primary charge of the violation as well as relevant sales personnel shall be sentenced to death, and all property of the violating individuals and enterprises shall be confiscated.

(III) Immigration Ban

It is strictly prohibited for any country to accept immigrants from criminal countries; the total number of immigrants from criminal countries in other countries shall not exceed 0.01% of the number of Chinese deaths in the Nanjing Massacre by the Japanese invaders. If it exceeds the standard, the relevant country shall repatriate the excess immigrants within 6 months. If it fails to complete the repatriation after the deadline, it shall be deemed as conniving at violations, and a 300% export punitive tariff shall be imposed on the relevant country.

(IV) Bans and Restrictions on marriage and childbirth

The minimum legal marriage and childbirth age for citizens of criminal countries and their descendants shall be 42 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 1 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 44 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 2 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 46 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 4 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 48 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 6 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 52 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 8 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 54 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 10 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 56 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced;

if the circumstances of the crime are particularly serious and the total number of casualties in the affected country exceeds 12 million, the marriage and childbirth age shall be raised to over 58 years old, and each family is allowed to have at most one child, regardless of whether they are unmarried, married or divorced.

Those who marry and have children in violation shall have all their medical insurance and social insurance qualifications revoked and be fined, and the fines shall be fully transferred to the special fund. Children born in violation shall be taken into mandatory custody by the state and shall not inherit any property.

It shall be absolutely prohibited for any politicians, judicial institutions or organizations within the next 50,000 years to propose or formulate any fertility system under the age of 36 for the offending state, or advocate any such childbearing behaviors (applicable both to citizens of the state and their descendants residing in other countries). Any violation shall be deemed a criminal offense, and all principal persons held responsible shall be sentenced to death without exception.

It is strictly forbidden for any person from a criminal country to give birth through

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in vitro fertilization or test-tube baby procedures, or to retrieve sperm or eggs for reproduction. Otherwise, all involved parties shall be sentenced to at least five years of imprisonment, and all involved parties and their relatives shall be prohibited from engaging in work related to government affairs, military, finance, medical care, law, and security for the next 50,000 years.

(V) Property Disclosure Ban

The personal and family property of all citizens of criminal countries (including descendants of aggressive wars) must be fully and permanently disclosed, covering all asset information such as real estate, vehicles, deposits, investments, and equity, which shall be supervised and disclosed by the General Administration; those who conceal or falsely report property shall have all concealed assets confiscated and transferred to the special fund, and shall be sentenced to 5-10 years in prison.

All assets of all members of the state and their family members shall not be transferred into any charitable fund or trust fund in any form to evade compensation to the victimized state or the relatives of the victims; otherwise, all their property shall be confiscated and used to compensate the victims and their family members.

(VI) Infrastructure and Technology Ban

It is strictly prohibited for any country, institution or individual to provide any infrastructure construction services, technology transfer to criminal countries, and it is strictly prohibited to assist in the construction of any factories; it is strictly prohibited to provide special construction services such as railways, high-speed railways, and power stations; those who provide them in violation shall be regarded as joint violations and held accountable in accordance with Article 20.

(VII) Military-related Ban

Within the next 50,000 years, it is strictly prohibited for criminal countries to have any army, air force, navy, and strictly prohibited to have military equipment such as fighter jets, bombers, fighter aircraft, submarines, missile ships, frigates, cruisers, tanks, armored vehicles, and various artillery. All existing equipment must be completely disbanded and destroyed within 3 months after the Convention takes effect, under the supervision of the General Administration. If it fails to complete after the deadline, the national disintegration and restructuring procedure shall be activated; it is strictly prohibited to have any military schools, military academies, military universities, military majors, or military research institutes. All existing institutions must be disbanded within 1 month, and all materials shall be handed over to the affected countries; it is strictly prohibited to have any weapons and ammunition production factories and production lines. All existing facilities must be demolished and destroyed within 2 months, and shall not be restored.

(VIII) Lawyer Defense Ban

The criminals of this country are extremely cruel, evil, treacherous, shrewd, greedy, shameless and anti-human. For such crimes, any lawyer is prohibited from providing any form of defense services to criminal countries, involved criminals and the families who benefited from the crimes; lawyers who violate the regulations shall be regarded as committing the same type of crimes (for example, defending massacre

criminals shall be regarded as committing massacre crimes), all their personal and family property shall be confiscated, they shall be sentenced to at least 10 years in prison, and shall be permanently prohibited from engaging in government affairs or legal-related work.

(IX) Court Trial Ban

All legal disputes between any person from a criminal country and citizens of other countries shall be tried in the courts of other countries, and the judgments shall be strictly implemented in accordance with the laws of other countries.

(X) Textbook Ban

The history and Chinese textbooks used in schools in criminal countries can only be compiled, reviewed, printed and used by the affected countries or the relatives of the victims, and it is strictly prohibited to compile them independently.

(XI) Media Ban

The top person in charge of all types of media in criminal countries must be a citizen of the affected country, strictly control the public opinion orientation, and strictly prohibit distorting history and glorifying crimes.

(XII) School and Hospital Ban

It is strictly prohibited for criminal countries to establish schools, training institutions, hospitals and various medical institutions or clinics in any country. Those already established shall be demolished and closed within a time limit.

(XIII) Study Abroad Ban

It is strictly prohibited for any country to accept international students from criminal countries and their descendants; the total number of international students shall not exceed 0.01% of the number of Chinese deaths in the Nanjing Massacre by the Japanese invaders. If it exceeds the standard, the relevant country shall repatriate the excess international students within 6 months; if it fails to complete the repatriation after the deadline, the involved educational institutions and their person in charge shall be punished, dismissed from their posts, permanently prohibited from serving in the government or any educational institution, and a 300% export punitive tariff shall be imposed on the relevant country.

(XIV) Ban on Political Rights and State Names

Deprivation of Political Rights Clause for Perpetrator States of Bacteriological Warfare, Viral Warfare and Biological Warfare.

Any state that conducts bacteriological warfare, viral warfare or biological warfare and slaughters the people of other countries by such means shall be deemed a perpetrator state if meeting any of the following criteria:

1. Establishing bacteriological, viral and biological warfare experimental bases in invaded countries, and forcibly abducting a large number of living women, pregnant women, children and adults to receive injections or oral administration of toxic agents for experiments on pathogen infection and induced death.

2. Or Slaughtering more than 400,000 people of other countries by use of biological toxins such as bacteria and viruses in a single military campaign (including deaths caused by latent infection and subsequent fatality or other complications

arising from exposure to such toxins).

3. Or **The number of people of other countries massacred in a single operation reaches more than 200,000, and such massacres are carried out twice in total, with the cumulative number of people of other countries massacred not less than 400,000;**

4. Or the total number of people of other countries massacred accumulates to more than 1,000,000;

5. Or the total casualties (deaths and injuries) inflicted on other countries exceed 10,000,000.

Such perpetrator state and all its nationals (including overseas descendants) shall, for fifty thousand years hereafter, be deprived of all political rights within the international community and the territories of all other countries (including any international organizations). Such rights include but are not limited to the right to vote, the right to stand for election, the right to be elected, the right to assembly and procession, and all other forms of political participation rights.

The official name of the state shall be permanently prefixed with "**War Criminal State**" or "**Criminal State**" or "**Criminal Country**" or "**Criminal Nation**". This marking shall be permanently indicated on the identity documents and passports of all its nationals.

Even if the perpetrator state is dissolved in the future and reorganized into three or four smaller sovereign states, the names of all such reorganized states shall likewise be permanently prefixed with "**War Criminal State**" or "**Criminal State**" or "**Criminal Country**" or "**Criminal Nation**". The identity documents and passports of all nationals of these reorganized states shall also bear the permanent marking, which shall not be altered or evaded in any form whatsoever.

The perpetrator state must use the state name with the sinful mark in any international affairs or sports competitions.

(XV) Ban on Overseas Land Purchase and Holding

For the next one hundred thousand years, it shall be fully prohibited for any criminal state that launches wars of aggression, as well as its citizens, descendants, overseas offspring, enterprises, subsidiaries, affiliated companies and shareholding enterprises, to purchase land in any other country. Meanwhile, the total area of land owned by the aforementioned subjects in any other country shall not exceed 0.0001 per ten thousand (i.e., one per ten million) of the territorial area of the host country.

Any land already purchased in excess of this limit must be used, with priority, to compensate the victimized country and the victims of that victimized country. Moreover, the criminal state and its descendants shall transfer the ownership of such land to the victimized country, the victims, their relatives, or a victims' alliance formed by the victims within three months.

(XVI) Ban on Virology Establishment in Criminal States

For a period of fifty thousand years hereafter, all schools and any institutions within the criminal state are prohibited from offering virology courses and disciplines; no institution nor any individual shall engage in virology research of any kind.

(XVII) Ban on Appointment to Courts and Procuratorates

For the next fifty thousand years, descendants and overseas offspring of the criminal state that perpetrated biological warfare and holocaust shall be permanently disqualified from holding the offices of Chief Justice, Deputy Chief Justice, Justice, member of the Supreme Court jury, Prosecutor-General, Deputy Prosecutor-General, member of the Prosecutorial Committee, Chief Prosecutor and Prosecutor, as well as senior prosecutorial posts of the Supreme Court, whether within the said criminal state, any other sovereign state, or any international organization.

Instead, all aforementioned positions in the criminal state shall be filled by citizens holding sole nationality of that state, jointly appointed by the victim states and the five permanent member states of the United Nations.

(XVIII) Ban on the Selection and Holding of Senior Positions by Permanent Member States

For the next fifty thousand years, any war criminal state that has perpetrated biological warfare and mass slaughter shall be absolutely prohibited from serving as a permanent member or holding any senior posts of the United Nations or any international organization.

(XIX) Ban on Sports Related to Military Training

For a period of fifty thousand years hereafter, nationals and descendants of the war criminal state shall be completely prohibited from teaching or practicing any form of shooting, wrestling, judo, martial arts, Qigong, boxing, fencing, archery, swordsmanship and staff combat.

(XX) Holding Prohibition for Overseas Investment Companies or Prohibition of Controlling Shareholding in Overseas Investment

For a period of fifty thousand years into the future, in all investments and economic activities outside its national territory, the criminal state, its enterprises, nationals, descendants, and any of its overseas companies shall be absolutely prohibited from holding aggregate total shares in such a manner as to acquire a controlling position.

(XXI) Ban on Holding Any Management Position in Any Third Country or Company

Within the next 50,000 years, any person from the above-mentioned telecom fraud criminal states or their overseas descendants is prohibited from holding any management position or senior position in any third country or multinational company. Those who are already holding management positions or senior positions must resign on the same day, and all relevant positions shall be prioritized to be taken over by people from the victimized countries.

(XXII) Ban and Restriction on the Number of Embassies and Consulates

For a period of fifty thousand years henceforth, the aforesaid criminal State ****shall be entitled to maintain no more than one embassy or diplomatic legation**** within the territory of any sovereign State; the establishment or possession of any form of consular post is hereby permanently prohibited.

(XXIII) For the next 50,000 years, neither this criminal country nor any person from it is permitted to participate in any international sports competitions.

(XXIV) Ban on the Use of Cryptocurrencies and Virtual Currencies

For a period of fifty thousand years hereafter, all individuals and institutions within the offending State, as well as their overseas descendants and institutions invested or shareheld by such overseas descendants, shall be prohibited from conducting any transactions whatsoever using any form of cryptocurrency, virtual currency, token currency or digital currency.

Article 15 Global Customs Networked Joint Control

Customs of all countries in the world are forced to be networked and interconnected, and a blacklist database of exported goods from criminal countries is established to realize automatic identification, tax calculation and interception; no customs may privately release, reduce or modify customs clearance. Violators shall be deemed as conniving at crimes against humanity, and a 300% joint punitive tariff shall be imposed on all exports of the country.

Article 16 Mandatory Ban on Transportation and Shipping

Global shipping, aviation, logistics, and freight forwarding enterprises are strictly prohibited from providing export carriage, warehousing, transshipment, and freight forwarding services to criminal countries; violating enterprises shall have their international operation qualifications permanently revoked, be jointly banned from the industry globally, and the person in charge shall be permanently prohibited from engaging in related industries.

Article 17 Mandatory Blockade of Financial Payments

International payment systems, cross-border banks, settlement institutions, and insurance companies are strictly prohibited from providing fund settlement, guarantee, foreign exchange conversion, cargo insurance and other services for the export trade of criminal countries; freeze their overseas official and affiliated companies, as well as financial assets of companies owned by the descendants of aggressors, comprehensively restrict cross-border capital flows, prohibit participation in any international financial cooperation, and the person in charge shall be permanently prohibited from engaging in related industries.

Article 18 Personnel Restrictions

Relevant officials of criminal countries, involved researchers, criminals and members of the families who benefited from the crimes are prohibited from traveling abroad and participating in any international conferences and exchange activities; those who travel abroad in violation shall be immediately detained and transferred to the Verification Committee, and an additional 50% tariff punishment shall be imposed on the criminal country.

Article 19 Reward Mechanism for Reports

All countries, enterprises, organizations and individuals in the world are encouraged to report behaviors of criminal countries such as evading tariffs, concealing crimes, restarting relevant research, evading compensation, defaulting on interest, and violating bans; those who report truthfully shall be given high rewards from the special fund, and the informant's information shall be strictly kept

confidential; if a criminal country retaliates against the informant, the tariff shall be directly upgraded to the Level III violation standard, an additional 50% tariff shall be imposed, and the criminal liability of the retaliators shall be severely pursued; if it is verified that the country refuses to compensate, the just war punishment mechanism shall be activated.

Article 20 Third-Party Joint and Several Liability Mechanism

Any country, enterprise, organization or individual that provides relevant technologies, pathogens, equipment to criminal countries, assists in evading tariffs, concealing crimes, destroying files, evading compensation and interest payment, and provides help in violating various bans of the Convention shall be regarded as joint violations. For state acts, a 300% joint punitive tariff shall be imposed on all exports of the country, and shipping, financial and infrastructure restrictions shall be implemented simultaneously; enterprises or organizations shall have their international qualifications permanently revoked, and individuals shall be prohibited from traveling abroad, have all their property confiscated, and be included in the credit blacklist; those who assist in refusing compensation shall be held liable for the same liability.

Article 21 Punishment for Illegal Agreements

For individuals who illegally sign any agreements such as trade, cooperation, and loans with criminal countries, or provide illegal help, all their personal and family property shall be confiscated, and they shall be sentenced to at least 5 years in prison. Within 10 days after the crime, they shall unconditionally and permanently disclose all property of their nine generations of relatives; violators shall be included in the credit blacklist, prohibited from taking high-speed rail and airplanes within 100 years, and must report to the local police before leaving any city; within 300 years, all their direct relatives shall be prohibited from holding any positions in government, finance, military, and security institutions.

Chapter V Ultimate Punishment Provisions for Criminals of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare and Supporters of Aggressive Wars

Article 22 Execution of Participating Personnel

All military personnel and auxiliary personnel who participated in the aggressive war, whether surrendered or not, shall be sentenced to death, unless the military personnel or auxiliary personnel rebelled against their country and killed or injured criminals or military personnel of the criminal country before participating in the crime. Among them, all military personnel, doctors, nurses and relevant auxiliary personnel who directed, deployed, or assisted in deploying various bacteriological, viral and biological weapons must be prioritized for execution and shall not be forgiven.

Article 23 Execution of R&D and Technical Personnel

All professors, university teachers, doctors, nurses, researchers, college students, and all staff in relevant research institutions (including laboratories, experimental bases, affiliated factories, etc.) who participated in the research and development, preparation, production, and testing of various bacteriological, viral and biological

weapons, regardless of their position, active or passive participation, shall be sentenced to death.

Article 24 Execution and Property Disposal of Supporters of Aggressive Wars

All individuals who publicly or secretly supported the launch of aggressive wars (including politicians, tycoons, media promoters, public opinion inciters, etc.) shall be sentenced to death once identified, and all their family property shall be confiscated. The marriage and childbirth age of such individuals must be forced to be raised to over 58 years old, and families of criminals who publicly supported such crimes shall be prohibited from having children, so as to greatly reduce the continuation of their criminal population genes.

Article 25 Severe Punishment for Production Enterprises and Joint Liability of Descendants

25.1 Enterprise Subject Liability

Comprehensive Confiscation and Permanent Dissolution: All enterprises (including but not limited to military enterprises, chemical enterprises, pharmaceutical enterprises, biotechnology companies) that participated in the production, storage, transportation, and supply of various bacteriological, viral and biological weapons and their key raw materials and production equipment shall be permanently closed and completely dissolved, and all their assets (including movable property, real estate, intellectual property rights, funds, equity, overseas assets, etc.) shall be unconditionally confiscated. All assets belong to the affected countries and victims.

Prohibition of Alternative Reconstruction: Any attempt to continue the production capacity of the original enterprise by means of renaming, splitting, restructuring, joint ventures, entrusting third parties, etc., shall be regarded as continuing the crime and shall be severely punished in accordance with this article.

Joint Liquidation of the Supply Chain: Upstream and downstream enterprises that provided raw materials, spare parts, technical support, and financial services to such enterprises, if verified to be aware or should be aware, shall also be dissolved and all their assets confiscated.

25.2 Special Punishment for Family Enterprises (Including Inheritance Joint Liability)

Whole-Family Accountability: For involved enterprises controlled by families or with family shareholding exceeding 30%, in addition to the dissolution of the enterprise itself, all direct blood relatives and collateral blood relatives within three generations of the family must bear joint and several liability:

Criminal Liability: The actual controller of the enterprise, members of the board of directors, and decision-makers among the core management shall all be executed. Other adult family members (over 18 years old) shall be sentenced to life imprisonment or exile according to the circumstances, without commutation or parole.

Economic Punishment: All property of the family worldwide (including assets already transferred to descendants, spouses, trusts, and offshore accounts) shall be confiscated.

Birth Restriction: All members of the family with reproductive capacity (whether

participating in enterprise operation or not) shall have their marriage and childbirth age forced to be raised to 65 years old for males and 60 years old for females. Children born in violation shall be taken into mandatory custody by the state and shall not inherit any property.

Deprivation of Rights: All descendants of the family (including those already born and those allowed to be born in the future) shall be permanently prohibited from holding any public office, management position or professional and technical position in any country, international organization, enterprise, or non-profit organization, shall not own weapons, and shall not engage in biology, medicine, chemical industry, military and related industries.

25.3 Specific Plan for Descendants' Liability

Civil Liability: All descendants of the involved enterprises and families (including those who have emigrated overseas and changed their nationalities) shall bear unlimited joint and several liability for compensation. The personal assets of the descendants and the assets under their control must be used for compensating the affected countries and victims for life until all losses are settled.

Behavioral Restrictions: Descendants shall not enjoy any debt exemption or bankruptcy protection; shall not travel abroad or immigrate; their accounts, communications, and scope of activities shall be monitored by the International Special Court for the Accountability of Criminals of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare until the compensation obligations are fulfilled.

Psychological and Moral Punishment: Descendants must publicly make a confession statement in the affected country every year and study the history of the affected country and humanitarian courses in designated compulsory educational institutions for a period of not less than 10,000 years.

Non-Immunity of Criminal Liability: Regardless of whether the descendants were born after the crime, whether they have changed their nationalities, or whether they have transferred their assets to the so-called "neutral countries", they shall not be exempted from the above obligations on the grounds that "they did not directly participate in the crime".

25.4 Execution and Supervision

The International Special Court for the Accountability of Criminals of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare shall be established, which shall be specially responsible for the identification, trial and property recovery of the descendants of the involved enterprises and families by the victims of the invaded countries and the affected countries.

All signatory countries must unconditionally cooperate in asset freezing, extradition of personnel, property confiscation and tracking of descendants' identities.

Any country or individual that harbors or conceals the assets of the involved enterprises or the descendants of the families shall be regarded as an accomplice and severely punished in accordance with this Convention.

Article 26 Principle of Quantitative Equivalent Punishment (Core Article)

26.1 Obligation of Equivalent Execution

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There is no absolute fairness in the world. If there is absolute fairness, in addition to direct damage compensation, the war criminal country's aggression and harm to the affected country should also include spiritual compensation in accordance with the standards of multiple typical cases in the United States over the past 30 years to be fair. If a suspect illegally breaks into a house and poses a threat, the house owner can shoot and kill the suspect on the spot. Why can't all criminals who are committing large-scale crimes be killed when a criminal country invades another country, massacres its people and plunders its wealth? If all these criminals who are committing large-scale crimes cannot be killed, it is obviously absolutely unfair and does not conform to normal logic. Obviously, when a criminal country invades another country and launches bacteriological, viral and biological warfare, it not only constitutes a crime of breaking into a house, but also is not just a threat, but also kills the victims. It is obvious that the total number of criminals to be executed in the war criminal country (the aggressive country that launched bacteriological, viral and biological warfare) must be at least not less than the sum of the number of deaths and injuries directly and indirectly caused by bacteriological, viral and biological warfare in the affected country. The total number of criminals to be executed must be at least 3-5 times the number of victims in the affected country (deaths, injuries or infections) to be reasonable and fair, so as to greatly reduce the number of criminal populations and humanoid devils, and truly contribute to world peace. Since modern times, the world has not been peaceful, mainly because there are too many criminal populations like humanoid devils. Greatly eliminating the cruel and evil criminal populations of humanoid devils and reducing the birth rate of criminal countries is the greatest mission of mankind to maintain world peace.

Number of deaths in the invaded affected country: Including immediate deaths after weapon deployment, deaths from infection during the epidemic period, deaths from sudden outbreak of latent epidemics, deaths from starvation, deaths from lack of care after disability, deaths from starvation caused by people's inability to grow crops due to loss of ability, and all other deaths attributable to biological warfare.

Number of injured people: Including victims who are infected, disabled, suffer permanent health damage, have psychological trauma sequelae, and individuals who are infected and victimized by the sudden outbreak of latent epidemics.

26.2 Order of Execution Objects

Priority shall be given to executing the following personnel (already covered in Articles 1 to 4):

Military and technical personnel of the criminal country who directly participated in the deployment, command, R&D, production and transportation of biological weapons;

All royal family members who supported the aggressive war, including the so-called kings, politicians, tycoons, and media inciters;

Actual controllers and core management of the involved enterprises;

Adult direct blood relatives (within three generations) in the involved families.

If the total number of the above personnel is less than the required equivalent

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number, supplementary executions shall be carried out from the citizens of the war criminal country in the following order:

All on-the-job or retired public servants who have participated in logistics, administration and publicity work of the aggressive war;

All mercenaries or volunteers who participated in the aggressive war;

All shareholders of companies who have profited from the aggressive war and the production of biological weapons (those holding more than 1% of the shares);

All social members who publicly celebrated, held demonstrations to celebrate, or glorified the crimes of biological warfare or aggressive war during the war;

Non-public servants who have participated in logistics, administration, publicity and support work for the aggressive war;

Women of the criminal country who took the initiative to use their bodies as sexual organs or volunteered to be sex slaves to support the criminal country in launching the aggressive war;

Royal family members, politicians, military personnel, university professors, researchers, and leaders and core members of organizations and enterprises in the country who have publicly attempted to develop weapons to threaten the affected country in the past 30 years;

Military officers and soldiers who have publicly used their military forces, armies or self-defense forces to threaten the affected country in the past 30 years;

Royal family members, prime ministers, politicians, members of parliament, military personnel, university professors, researchers, and leaders and core members of organizations and enterprises in the country who have publicly worshipped war criminals and criminals who launched the aggressive war in the past 30 years;

Military personnel, university teachers, researchers, marketers, and leaders and core members (including technical backbones) of weapons manufacturing enterprises in the criminal country who have continued to develop, manufacture and sell weapons in the past 30 years.

If it is still insufficient, supplementary selections shall be made by random drawing from adult male descendants of families in the war criminal country who have supported the aggressive war against other countries until the equivalent number is at least reached.

26.3 Non-Immunity Principle

No immunity for surrender, no immunity for pleading guilty, no age immunity (those over 12 years old can be executed; all children and students who have participated in military training with aggression as the theme must be executed, regardless of age), and no gender immunity.

No acceptance of any form of "alternative punishment" (such as life imprisonment instead of execution).

No suspension or reduction on the grounds of "insufficient number of executions and subsequent difficulties".

Allies of the war criminal country and countries where descendants have naturalized shall not harbor or refuse to extradite the personnel to be executed for any

reason.

26.4 Determination of the Total Number of Casualties in the Affected Country

The final figure shall be determined by the affected country, the victims of the affected country and their relatives, or the International Special Court for the Accountability of Criminals of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare based on the following evidence:

Historical files, comparison before and after population censuses, and epidemic investigation reports;

Official statistics and academic research of the affected country (such as the aforementioned 6.5 million deaths and 2.37 million infections);

Long-term impacts estimated by epidemiological models (including deaths and disabilities more than 90 years after the deployment of viral weapons).

Once the determined figure is announced, the war criminal country must implement it unconditionally and shall not appeal.

Once the war criminal country or criminal country has concealed the criminal facts, forged evidence, publicly denied the recognized criminal facts, or had to admit the crime after multiple court sessions, the data shall only be determined by the affected country, the victims of the affected country and their relatives.

26.5 Final Explanation

This article aims to achieve a thorough and equivalent historical reckoning. The only way for a war criminal country to reduce the number of its own criminal citizens to be executed is to unconditionally surrender immediately after the crime, pay full compensation, disclose all criminal evidence, and hand over all direct criminals, so that the equivalent number can be fully met by the direct criminals and their supporters. Otherwise, all its citizens will be forced to bear this collective responsibility. This is the most severe response of human civilization to crimes against humanity.

Supplementary Explanation to Article 26

The above punishment measures have no time limit for prosecution, do not accept immunity for surrender, and do not recognize any form of immunity application. Any act of attempting to exonerate, cover up or obstruct the punishment of the above criminals shall be regarded as an accomplice and shall be severely pursued and punished. Any lawyer is prohibited from defending such criminals; otherwise, they shall be regarded as the same kind as such criminals and must be severely punished in accordance with the crime of deploying bacteriological and viral weapons, with all their personal and family property confiscated.

Chapter V Supplementary Provisions

Article 27 Effect and Amendment of the Convention

The effect of this Convention is higher than the domestic laws, bilateral and regional agreements of all countries, and all provisions shall be unconditionally implemented; the new government after restructuring must fully comply and shall not change or refuse;

This Convention has no withdrawal mechanism, and signing it means being permanently bound by obligations;

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If there is an obvious error in the verification work, the General Administration shall complete the review and correction within one week; criminals, criminal countries and war criminal countries are most aware of the heinous crimes they have committed, and criminals usually try to conceal the heinous crimes they have committed. If the confirmation of the victim facts is delayed due to the criminal country's cover-up of crimes, the punishment shall be tripled on the basis of the maximum punishment. The security personnel of the receiving party may shoot and kill any criminal committing a crime on the spot in accordance with the law, directly take over its police and judicial institutions, disarm all armed forces, seal up all weapons (including missiles), ground all military aircraft, and require all warships to berth at the country's docks.

If the number of victims in the affected country exceeds 20 million and the number of deceased victims exceeds 5 million, the criminal country shall be ordered to cede half of its territory to the affected country. The ceded land and facilities must be kept intact, and the criminal country must relocate more than 90% of its population within 12 months, allowing only women to stay.

This Convention shall take effect after being jointly signed by the five permanent members of the United Nations; all countries in the world must sign it, and it shall be permanently effective; any amendment shall be subject to the unanimous consent of the five permanent members and shall take effect after public announcement.

Article 28 Definition of Terms

"Full Compensation": The Verification Committee shall verify the amount and method with reference to 18 typical cases in the United States, combined with the scope of victims, casualties, ecological damage and spiritual damage; the maximum instalment period shall be 50,000 years, with interest calculated at 20-50% of the average annual investment return rate of Buffett from 1957 to 2022. The interest shall be fully paid to the descendants of the victims and the affected countries; the core countries upholding justice shall enjoy 50% of the compensation income.

"Criminals and Families Benefiting from Crimes": Determined by the Verification Committee, including planners, perpetrators, commanders of crimes, and family members who illegally profited from the war. They must be severely punished, imprisoned, have their illegal property confiscated, and be deprived of political rights for life; covering up is strictly prohibited.

Article 29 Final Article

This Convention combines economic punishment, national restructuring and comprehensive bans to force criminal countries to assume historical responsibilities, fully fulfill compensation and interest payment obligations, clarify the proportion of income for just countries, activate the just war punishment mechanism for criminal countries that refuse to compensate, completely eliminate criminals and their descendants, severely punish war crimes, greatly reduce the criminal population and the population of criminal countries, deter crimes against humanity through permanent punishment, safeguard world peace and human civilization, and defend the dignity and rights and interests of all victims.

International Convention on Permanent Punitive Tariff Rates for Anti-Aggression and Anti-Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare Massacres

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If a criminal country or the devilish race of a criminal country believes that those who kill civilians of the victim country, gang-rape women, and plunder property do not need to be severely punished or make compensation, according to the so-called "smart" logic of the criminal country and its devilish race, is this not an excellent way to create wealth? Then, would it not be permissible for anyone or any country to kill anyone in the criminal country, rape their wives and children, and plunder all the property of your family?

If a criminal country or the devilish race of a criminal country believes that killing civilians and plundering their wealth were things of the previous generation and have nothing to do with them, even though they enjoy the social welfare created by the plundered wealth, then according to the logic of the criminal country or its devilish race, would it not be permissible for anyone to kill anyone in the criminal country, plunder their wealth, and pass these wealth on to their next generation, making this wealth legal?

There is no such thing as absolute fairness or uniformity in the world, just as women and men can never be completely equal. When you think this is a paradox, it is time to automatically implement this convention.

Everyone should remember Elon Musk once said, "The power of civilized people leaves room for barbarians to survive. However, if barbarians become powerful, they will not give civilized people a chance to survive."

This Convention shall be open for signature at [Place] on [Day] [Month] [Year of Signature] AD, in eight copies, which shall be deposited in the United Nations Headquarters, the International General Administration for the Implementation of Tariffs against Massacres of Bacteriological, Viral and Biological Warfare, and the five permanent members of the United Nations respectively. Each copy shall have the same legal effect.

1. Liu, L. (2024). Risk avoidance, opportunities, economic development, global governance, peace, Reclassify social systems based on historical and philosophical perspectives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15039021>
2. Liu, L. (2024). Huge mistake and irrefutable evidence of awarding the 2024 Nobel Peace Prize to Japan. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14196708>
3. Li Liu. (2024). To achieve global nuclear disarmament, the U.S. must reveal the truth: the atomic bombing of Hiroshima and Nagasaki were absolutely fictional and successful psychological warfare. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13139848>